

MycoTWIN-Enhancing Research and Innovation Capacity of TUBITAK MRC Food Institute
on Management of Mycotoxigenic Fungi and Mycotoxins
GA no.952337

D1.1 Report on 1st Year Activities (summer schools, technical visits, short-term trainings, expert visits)

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1. SUMMARY

This document includes information regarding the summer schools, technical visits, short-term trainings and expert visits planned to be held in the 1st year of the project to increase the national and international awareness of MycoTWIN.

This deliverable is defined as an output of WP1 which is “Report on 1st year activities (summer schools, technical visits, short-term trainings, expert visits)”.

2. INTRODUCTION

MycoTWIN project aims to significantly strengthen a defined field of research (researches on mycotoxigenic fungi and mycotoxins) in TUBITAK (an institute from a widening country, Turkey) by linking it with two internationally-leading research institutes in Member States Countries which are CNR (Italy) and UV (Spain). This collaboration will enable TUBITAK to increase knowledge, experience, and skills of its research staff, to develop dissemination activities, to achieve rapid and effective communication with stakeholders, to raise awareness at national and international level, to strengthen cooperation with international leading institutes, to formulate scientific strategy for further researches and to promote the involvement of its young researchers in this field.

The collaboration program will focus on experience and knowledge exchange, be provided through the organization of joint activities. For this purpose, it is planned to organize a series of summer schools, short-term trainings in leading partners (CNR and UV) and technical visits not only to leading partner institutes but also other institutes and industries in Europe and Turkey. Moreover, expert visits from CNR and UV to TUBITAK and Turkish stakeholders are planned to share knowledge and experience of leading partners.

3. ACTIVITIES

3.1 Summer Schools

4 summer schools were planned to be realized within the 1st year of the project;

School 1 (in CNR): Rapid and official methods for mycotoxin detection and toxigenic fungi identification (morphological and molecular approaches) in wheat

School 2 (in CNR): Strategies for minimization of mycotoxins and toxigenic fungi in food chains

School 3 (in UV): LC-MS/MS multi-mycotoxins methods for the analysis of the nuts and dried fruits

School 4 (in UV): GC-MS/MS multi-mycotoxins methods for the analysis of cereals and derivate products

All summer schools were postponed to the next years due to Covid 19 pandemic situation and restrictions.

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3.2 Technical Visits

2 technical visits from TUBITAK to partner institutes and industries in partner countries were planned to be realized within the 1st year of the project;

Visit 1: CNR-ISPA + Besana

Visit 2: UV + Importaco Company

The technical visits were postponed to the next years due to Covid 19 pandemic situation and restrictions.

3.3. Short-Term Trainings

1st short-term training on “Pre and post-harvest management for mycotoxins and toxigenic fungi minimization in dried fruits including nuts, cereals and spices; Mycotoxin monitoring and toxigenic fungi identification” was planned to be realized in CNR at the 1st year of the project. It was postponed to the next years due to Covid 19 pandemic situation and restrictions.

3.4 Expert Visits

1st expert visit from CNR-ISPA and UV to TUBITAK MRC Food Institute was planned to be realized within the 1st year of the project. It was postponed to the next years due to Covid 19 pandemic situation and restrictions.